

Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM): Appendices, Figures, and Tables

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Appendix S1: Construction of the Quantile-Kendall Plot

A-1: Overview

The Quantile-Kendall plot (Hirsch, 2018) can be viewed as an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) technique. Although it includes information that arises out of formal hypothesis tests, it is not a test, but rather a graphic that is designed to give an overall impression of the nature of the discharge (streamflow) trend over some period of record over the entire flow duration curve and is derived using daily mean discharges measured at a streamgage. Further description of the method and the associated software can be obtained from <https://owi.usgs.gov/blog/Quantile-Kendall/>.

The method can be used to explore trends over the full range of discharge (from low to high flows) and can be applied to changes across annual, seasonal (defined as any contiguous set of months), or monthly time periods. In this paper, Quantile-Kendall plots were generated to explore annual discharge trends (Figs. 4 and 5 in the paper, and Choquette et al., 2018) and monthly discharge trends (Fig. S4-1, in ESM below) at the WLEB study sites. The Quantile-Kendall plot is designed for analysis of daily discharge records, preferably with a length on the order of two decades or more. The method is described here as applied to climatic years (April 1 through March 31) for a period of 29 climatic years, using daily discharge records for the time-period April 1, 1987, through March 31, 2016. “Daily discharge” refers to the average discharge at a streamgage site on a given day, typically reported in m³ per second or ft³ per second.

For simplicity, we describe here the analysis for full years (rather than seasons or months), and for simplicity we treat each year as having 365 days, ignoring leap years. Section A-2 details how leap years are handled. For each year, the 365 daily discharge values are sorted from smallest to largest. These values are assigned a rank (k) where $k = 1, 2, \dots, 365$, with 1 being the smallest and 365 being the largest discharge value. For the full time-series of n years, all rank 1 discharges are evaluated as a time series of n years in length and the results of that analysis are summarized by a slope and by a two-sided significance level (or p-value). This process is repeated 365 times, so that for each rank (k) there is a slope with an associated significance level and likelihood value. The specifics of the trend analysis are provided below in Section A-3. The graphic shows the trend slope for each of the 365 ranks, and color coding is used to indicate the likelihood that the estimated trend direction (upwards or downwards) is correct (see Section A-5). The results are arrayed on the plot with low discharges to the left, median discharge in the middle, and high discharges to the right. Details of the plot construction and the likelihood characterization appear in Sections A-4 and A-5, respectively. A summary in Section A-6 includes interpretations and caveats associated with Quantile-Kendall plots and potential uses of the plots to increase understanding and to improve modeling of stream discharge responses to climatic and land-use/water-use changes.

A-2: Details of data preparation

The method used for construction of the Quantile-Kendall plot requires each year to have exactly 365 daily discharge values. This means that for those years that contain a February 29 date (leap years), the number of daily values needs to be shortened from 366 to 365. This is accomplished as follows: (1) for each year with 366 days, the daily values are sorted from the smallest discharge value to the largest discharge value; (2) the median of the 366 values is computed and is equal to the mean of the 183rd and 184th ranked values; and (3) the 183rd and 184th ranked values are discarded from the data set and replaced by the one median value. This approach to

standardizing the number of days per year is preferable to discarding a specific day of the year (such as February 29 or December 31) because it avoids deleting values that may be at the lower or higher end of the discharge distribution. Such an approach would introduce a bias in the estimates of trends in the extremes of the distribution.

In application to seasons or months that include February 29, a similar approach is used to reduce the number of daily values during leap years. When that period has an even number of values in leap years (say the season is defined as the months of January and February, for a total of 60 days during leap years) the same procedure described above, replacing the two middle values with their mean, is the method used. When the period that includes February 29 has an odd number of values in leap years (say the season is defined as the months of January, February and March, for a total of 91 days in leap years) the method used is to simply delete the median value from the data set. The remainder of this description of the algorithm considers data sets that have already been standardized in this manner.

A-3: Specifics of the trend analysis for each rank

Define $Q_{k,j}$ as the k^{th} order statistic of the 365 daily mean discharge values for year j . Thus, the lowest daily value in year j , would be $Q_{1,j}$ and the highest daily value in year j would be $Q_{365,j}$. Having ranked the data for each year in the trend period (no partial years are allowed) a modified version of the Mann-Kendall trend test is applied 365 times, once for each value of k . The results of each of these 365 tests are captured in an attained two-sided p-value for the test, which we denote as p_k . It is computed using the version of the Mann-Kendall test, which is adjusted for serial correlation (see Yue et al., 2002; and Zhang et al., 2001). The test is carried out using the `zyp.zhang` function in the `zyp` R-package (Bronaugh and Werner, 2013). The null hypothesis is that the $Q_{k,j}$ values are identically distributed across all values of j (that is, across all years). The alternative hypothesis is that the distribution changes monotonically over time. It is robust against lag-one serial correlation, provided that the correlation structure of these annual values is auto-regressive lag one.

This modification from the standard Mann-Kendall test for trend mitigates the tendency for actual Type I error rates to be higher than the nominal Type I error rate when the data are generated by a process that is lag-one auto-regressive but trend-free. This makes it a slightly more conservative test than the standard Mann-Kendall trend test in those cases where the data are independent and identically distributed. The p-values associated with the modified Mann-Kendall test are computed in the Quantile-Kendall software, which also produces the time-series graphics shown in Figure 3 (of the paper). These attained p-values are shown in the graphics because they are a familiar indicator of the strength of the evidence in support of rejecting the null hypothesis. In section A-5 we describe the conversion of p-values to the likelihood measures presented in the Quantile-Kendall plot.

In conjunction with the modified Mann-Kendall test, a slope is estimated for each value of k , using the Thiel-Sen robust line slope estimate (see Sen, 1968 or Thiel, 1950). The Thiel-Sen robust line is widely used in hydrology to estimate the slope of a monotonic trend. This estimate is used in preference to an ordinary least squares estimate of trend slope because it is resistant to the influence of outliers. The Thiel-Sen slope estimate has the property that the slope estimate will always have the same sign as the Mann-Kendall test statistic, τ , and when $\tau = 0$ the Thiel-Sen slope estimate is also zero. To stabilize the variance in cases where trends are very large, the Thiel-Sen slopes are calculated here using the natural logarithms of the daily discharge values. This results in a dimensionless slope estimate. To make the results more meaningful, this slope is transformed to a trend

expressed as percent change per year. The transformation is based on the idea that a linear trend in log units, after re-transformation, becomes an exponential trend in discharge units. The conversion is this:

$$b = 100 \cdot (e^B - 1)$$

where b is the trend slope expressed in units of percent per year, and B is the Thiel-Sen slope estimate based on the natural logarithms of the data.

Although it is not shown on the graphical output, the total percentage change over a period of m years can be expressed as:

$$b(m) = 100 \cdot (e^{B \cdot m} - 1)$$

where $b(m)$ is the percentage change over a period of m years. It is worth noting, that when B is large the non-linearity of this relationship can be important. For example, the trend slope (B) of Honey Creek annual mean discharge (lower right panel of Figure 3, in paper) is 0.026, and hence b is approximately 2.6 percent per year. But if we look at a 30-year time horizon ($m = 30$), the change over that period would be about 118 percent, which is much greater than if we simply multiplied the 2.6 percent by 30 years, which would indicate a 78-percent change.

A-4: Construction of the graphic

The 365 estimates of slope in percent change per year are denoted as b_k . These values are plotted against the standard normal deviate for the Weibull plotting position for the given k value.

$$z_k = \Phi^{-1} \left(\frac{k}{N + 1} \right)$$

Where N is the number of ranked days in the trend period, e.g. year, season, or month. For example, for analysis based on the full year, $N = 365$. If the analysis were for only January data, $N = 31$. Φ^{-1} is the inverse cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution, and z_k is the standard normal deviate.

Although the points are plotted at (z_k, b_k) , the horizontal axis of the plot is labeled by the rank on the upper scale and by the values of $k/(N + 1)$ denoted as the “daily non-exceedance probability” on the lower scale. The fact that the standard normal distribution is used to set the scale of the horizontal axis does not imply that the discharge data follow a normal distribution, it is simply a means of achieving a higher degree of resolution for the lowest and highest discharges and less resolution near the middle of the discharge distribution.

A-5: Likelihood characterizations (shown in color on the plot)

The plotted points are shown in a color that corresponds with the likelihood (L_k) that the sign of the true slope is the same as the sign of the estimated slope. Higher values of L_k indicate a higher confidence that if the estimate indicates a positive trend then the true trend is positive or that if the estimate indicates a negative trend then the true trend is negative. The value of L_k is computed from the two-sided attained significance level p_k , specifically $L_k = (1 - (p_k/2))$. The likelihood designations follow the pattern used by Hirsch et al. (2015) and are shown in this table.

Likelihood designation	Range of likelihood values
Highly likely	0.95 to 1.00
Very likely	0.90 to <0.95
Likely	0.67 to <0.90
Uncertain	0.50 to <0.67

A-6: Caveats and summary

The Quantile-Kendall plot should be considered a type of EDA technique and not a tool of hypothesis testing, even though it has the results of hypothesis tests embedded in it. Because the order statistics for any given year are highly correlated with each other, the b_k values are also highly correlated with each other and the associated Mann-Kendall test results (the p_k values) are as well. Thus, the information content of the results is not equivalent to conducting 365 independent statistical tests. Although each of the 365 tests is a test for trend at some point on the frequency distribution, the overall result shown on the Quantile-Kendall plot should not be viewed as a test for trend in discharge, rather it is an exploratory graphic that identifies the direction and strength of the discharge trend as it varies across the entire frequency distribution of discharge.

One aspect of the plots can appear odd in some cases. In particular, near the left edge (low-flow) portion of the plot, a number of the b_k values may plot as being exactly equal to zero. This arises when a substantial number of pair-wise differences in discharge are exactly zero, resulting in a slope estimate of exactly zero. If we were to compute the Thiel-Sen slope on a data set generated from a random number generator for any continuous distribution, pair-wise differences of exactly zero would have a vanishingly small probability of occurring, and thus a slope estimate of exactly zero would have a vanishingly small probability of occurring. The reason that these slope estimates of exactly zero are common in real data sets is because of the accuracy and reporting conventions for discharge measurements. The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) reports these values to 3 significant figures for higher flows but only to 1 or 2 significant figures at lower flows¹. As a result, a substantial number of the pair-wise comparisons that are used in computing the slope estimate for the lower range of flows have a non-trivial probability of having a difference of exactly zero. Then, when all pair-wise slopes are sorted and B is computed as the median of all of these pair-wise slopes, B may end up being exactly zero. This explains the slightly odd

¹ USGS streamflow reporting protocols: Accuracy of Field Data and Computed Results: "Values of daily mean discharge are shown to the nearest hundredth of a cubic foot per second for discharges of less than 1 ft³/s; to the nearest tenths between 1.0 and 10 ft³/s; to whole numbers between 10 and 1,000 ft³/s; and to three significant figures above 1,000 ft³/s." [at <https://wdr.water.usgs.gov/current/documentation.html>]

appearance of some of the plots (particularly true when applied to individual months as in Fig. S4-1, in ESM below).

To some extent, the patterns of results shown on a Quantile-Kendall plot can be described in words. For example, a result that goes from large negative trend slopes at the left edge of the figure to large positive values at the right edge (i.e. low discharges getting lower and high discharges getting higher) would be indicative of increasing variability in daily flows. Conversely, large positive values at the left side and large negative values at the right side are indicative of decreasing variability in daily flows; that is, reflecting increasing low flows and decreasing high flows. If most of the entire result is in the positive range, but the points show little slope, then we can say that discharges are generally increasing over the period being analyzed, but the distribution of daily flows is neither becoming more variable or less variable when variability is expressed as a coefficient of variation; all flows are increasing by a similar percentage. Conversely, if the results are mostly in the negative range we can say that discharges are generally decreasing but if the slope is relatively horizontal, then we can say that the distribution of daily flows is neither becoming more variable or less variable.

The Quantile-Kendall plot is a potentially powerful tool for the study of hydrologic change. Applying it to a set of discharge records across a region may be useful for classifying patterns and magnitudes of hydrologic change. The use of the Quantile-Kendall plot could contribute to evaluating the roles of climate-based versus landscape-based drivers of change in a region. It may also be useful for evaluating various deterministic models of hydrologic change. If one ran a deterministic model that produced simulated daily discharges, in hindcast mode, using real historical forcings of the model (these could be precipitation and temperature inputs or they could be greenhouse gas inputs or land alteration parameters), one could explore the model outputs using a Quantile-Kendall plot and compare that modeled output to the Quantile-Kendall plot based on actual historical daily record. Similarities and differences between the plots generated in these two ways can be a useful diagnostic for the predictive power of the model being used.

The current implementation of the Quantile-Kendall plot (available at <https://owi.usgs.gov/blog/Quantile-Kendall/>) is not designed to be used with discharge records that have data gaps nor is it designed to be used with records that have zero or negative discharges at any time in the record. Conceptually, the method can be extended to these cases, but at this time the code has not been developed or tested to deal with such cases.

Any use of trade, firm, or product names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the U.S. Government.

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Appendix S2: Implementation of the Generalized Flow Normalization Method

Background information on the original method and R-software, which focus on stationary flow normalization (FNS), appears in Hirsch and De Cicco (2015) and Hirsch et al. (2015). The necessary software and documentation for implementing the generalized flow normalization (FNG) method described here are part of the EGRET 3.0 R package; and the related modifications of the Weighted Regressions on Time, Discharge, and Season (WRTDS) Bootstrap Test, which provides trend uncertainty estimates, are included in the EGRETci 2.0 R package. Both packages, which include user guides, can be found at <https://cran.r-project.org/>. The nutrient and discharge (streamflow) model input data, in a form that can be input to the EGRET software, and the trend output results from the FNG method for the trend sites used in this study are available online from Choquette et al. (2018).

The EGRET 3.0 and EGRETci 2.0 R packages allow the user to designate for each year being analyzed (denoted year j), a specific set of years to be used to characterize the probability density function (pdf) of daily mean discharge, abbreviated as “discharge” here, for each day of that year (denoted day i). As in the original formulation of WRTDS flow-normalization (defined by Hirsch, et al., 2010), this pdf is determined using a non-parametric approach, which approximates it as a set of point masses based on the set of observed discharges for day i over a specified set of years, or time “window”.

Using the EGRET software to implement FNG, the user must specify the length of the time-window (in years) which determines the number of years used to create the discharge pdf associated with any given year j . The window length (denoted t_w) is set by the user and is always an odd number of years. To set the value for t_w the EGRET software uses an argument called *windowSide* that is specified by the user as an integer value to calculate $t_w = (2 \cdot \text{windowSide}) + 1$. In this study the value selected for *windowSide* is 7, which means that t_w is always 15 years. In the specific case of the 1995-2015 nutrient trends in this study, the flow-normalized fluxes are computed for the years 1995 and 2015. The set of years used to estimate the pdf of discharge for 1995 is 1988 – 2002 (the 15-year period centered on 1995). That means that the estimated pdf (denoted as $\hat{g}_{i,j}(Q)$ in the paper) for each day i of the year j ($j=1995$) is made up of the 15 observed discharge values for day i of each of the 15 years in that period. All sites in this study had discharge records extending back to at least 1987.

When the start or end year of the trend period falls near the beginning or end of the discharge period of record, the window-selection procedure is modified as follows. The discharge data available for this study ends with water year 2016, so the set of years used to estimate the pdf of discharge for the year 2015 is 2002-2016. This means that the estimated discharge pdf for day i of year j ($j=2015$) is made up of the 15 observed daily discharge values for day i of each of the 15 years in that period. To generalize from that, the EGRET 3.0 software determines the set of years from which it draws its historical sample for year j from a set of t_w years which is symmetrical around year j , but if it is not possible for it to be symmetrical (because j is too near the start or end of the available discharge record) then the software adjusts the period such that it ends with the last year of the record if j is near the end of the record, or adjusts the period such that it starts with the first year of the record, if j is near the start of the record. This windowing process is also described, along with a graphical presentation, in the “Guide to EGRET 3.0 enhancements” (section 3.2) which is part of the EGRET 3.0 software release.

The software also provides for the possibility of designating a date at which the discharge pdf (for all days in the year) may have shifted due to some management change in the watershed (e.g. construction or removal of a dam, or a major change in diversions into or out of the watershed). In these cases, the set of years used for year

j is constrained to fall entirely on one side of that shift date. This approach was not used in this study but is part of the flexibility of the software.

Selecting an appropriate value for the parameter *windowSide* is subjective and should be informed through trial and error based on the time series of flow normalized flux estimates produced using different values of *windowSide*. Establishing an “optimal” value for *windowSide* would depend on an ability to separate the true nonstationarity of discharge from the serial dependence of discharge after removal of trend. If *windowSide* is too narrow, then the time series of flow-normalized flux values will show large year-to-year variations influenced by the random year-to-year variations in discharge. At the other extreme, where *windowSide* is set equal to a value greater than half of the total length of the discharge period of record, it becomes equivalent to using stationary flow-normalization and the time series will be very smooth. In this situation, the flow-normalization removes not only the effect of random year-to-year variations in discharge but also removes the effect of discharge trends from the flow-normalized flux. Further use of the FNG method should reveal more guidance on best practices for setting the *windowSide* argument. In spite of the inherent subjectivity of this important parameter, it is our judgment that using an arbitrary value, such as 7 years, is preferable to either of the two alternatives (applying no flow normalization or simply assuming stationarity of discharge).

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Appendix S3: Selected watershed attributes of the study sites

Data summarized here for the 10 watersheds evaluated for trends (Table 1 in the paper) include information on reservoir storage, streamflow alterations, and temporal changes in tillage practices, livestock production, manure and farm fertilizer, and crop production.

Streamflow alteration and reservoir storage

Table S3-1 summarizes information on reservoirs and flow alterations upstream of the study sites (Falcone et al., 2010; Falcone, 2011 and 2015; U.S. Geological Survey, 2017). Total upstream reservoir storage volume in 2009, expressed as days of average streamflow, ranges from 0 to 1.6 days for the sites ROCK, HONE, STMF, and STMD; 9 days for SAND; 20 to 28 days for MAUW, MAUN, and STJO; and 52 to 59 days for RAIS and CUYA (Table S3-1). Site STJO on the St. Joseph River is located about 5 km downstream of Cedarville Reservoir (1,900 megaliters (ML) storage). Upstream of Cedarville Reservoir, St. Joseph River flows are periodically diverted into Hurshtown Reservoir (6,400 ML storage) located on a tributary of the St. Joseph River. Streamflows at HONE and ROCK are considered minimally affected by regulation (Lins, 2012; Falcone, 2015). Only two of the sites show notable changes in reservoir storage during recent decades, comparing 1990 and 2009 values reported in Falcone (2015): total reservoir storage volume upstream of HONE and SAND sites increased slightly by 1.1 and 1.0 days of average flow, respectively. Upstream flow diversions have been noted for the sites STMF, STMD, STJO, and CUYA (Table S3-1; U.S. Geological Survey, 2017).

Conservation Tillage

Conservation tillage (inclusive of no till, mulch till, and strip till, and high-residue management practices) increased from about 5-10 percent of croplands during the late 1980s to 55-80 percent in 2007 in the trend watersheds (Fig. S3-1) (Jarvie et al., 2017; Remegio Confessor, Heidelberg Univ., written commun., February 24, 2017). Between 1995 and 2012 in the MAUW, SAND, and RAIS watersheds, where long-term estimates were available, conservation tillage increased from an estimated 20-35 percent to 50-75 percent of croplands. Between 2007 and 2012, additional estimates are available for the St. Joseph and St. Marys River basins in the upper Maumee basin; during 2007 about 55-85 percent of croplands were in conservation tillage in these 5 watersheds, which subsequently decreased by about 5 to 10 percent by 2012 in 4 of the watersheds. There was a continued increase in conservation tillage, by about 5 percent, in the RAIS through 2012 (Fig. S3-1).

Livestock Production

During 1982-2012, estimates of watershed mean densities of poultry, swine, and cattle were consistently highest for the 2 sites in the St. Marys River basin (STMD and STMF), where all three livestock types increased over time (Fig. S3-2) (Falcone, 2015). The average values of the two St. Marys basin sites during the period 1992 to 2012 ranged from 1,656 to 2,474 chickens per km², 9 to 13 times higher than the average of the other seven trend watersheds in the western Lake Erie basin (WLEB); and ranged from 85 to 140 hogs per km² and 26 to 35 cows per km², which were 2 to 4 times higher than the respective averages of the other seven WLEB trend watersheds. Poultry livestock values for the area upstream of STMD nearly tripled between 1982-2002 (from about 900 to 2,650 head per km²) then remained fairly constant between 2002 and 2012; and swine livestock doubled between 1982-2012. The two St. Marys sites show 2012 estimated numbers of chickens, hogs, and cows exceeding 2,200, 130, and 33 head per km², respectively. These livestock estimates were derived using county data adjusted for agricultural land-use extent and proportion of watershed within the county, as described in Falcone (2015). See section "Manure and Farm Fertilizer" for additional comments regarding locations of confined animal feeding operations (CAFOs) and livestock estimates for these watersheds.

Manure and Farm Fertilizer

Watershed mean values of phosphorus and nitrogen from manure and farm fertilizer (from Falcone, 2017a and b) for the 10 study basins are shown in Figs. S3-3 and S3-4. These values are estimates derived using county-level inventories, scaled to the watershed level using land-use classifications, at 60-m grid-interval resolution, as described in Falcone (2017a and b). Source data on livestock population inventories were reported at 5-year intervals (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2014), and fertilizer inventories were reported annually (Association of American Plant Food Control Officials, 2012). Among these study sites, the Cuyahoga River site (CUYA) consistently shows the lowest values of manure and fertilizer (Fig. S3-3), reflecting the much lower extent of row-crop land use in this basin (Table 1 in the paper).

Annual values and changes over time in manure-P and -N were substantially larger for the two St. Marys sites (STMD and STMF) compared to the other sites, and show 36- to 44-percent increases between 1994 and 2012 (Tables S3-2 and S3-3). Peak values during this period occurred in 2007 when manure-P and -N estimates at these two sites were more than 3 to 4 times that of most other sites (Figs. S3-3 and S3-4). The next-highest manure-N and -P values among study sites occurred at the 2 sites downstream on the main stem Maumee River (MAUN and MAUW), influenced by inputs from the St. Marys River watershed.

Although the annual fertilizer-P and -N estimates for the trend watersheds (Fig. S3-3) show temporal fluctuations during the past 25 years, both N- and P-fertilizer show overall declines averaging about 1-2 percent per year between 1994 and 2012 (Tables S3-2 and S3-3). The annual fluctuations may in part reflect commodity-price influences and fertilizer purchases for use over more than one year, given the estimates are derived using fertilizer-sales records. The 1987-2012 annual fertilizer estimates among these watersheds show consistently higher values for both fertilizer-P and -N in the Sandusky basin sites (SAND, HONE, and ROCK), the St. Marys basin sites (STMD, STMF), and the lower Maumee basin site (MAUW) (Figs. S3-3 and S3-4).

Only the St. Joseph basin site (STJO) showed a 1994-2012 increase in fertilizer-N, although slight (11%), in contrast to -22 to -37 percent reductions at most other WLEB sites (Tables S3-2 and S3-3). STJO showed the lowest 1994-2012 reduction in fertilizer-P (-4% compared to -26 to -47% at most other WLEB sites). The River Raisin site (RAIS) P-fertilizer pattern is somewhat unique among the WLEB sites, showing a relatively linear long-term decline during 1987-2012, with a larger, -47 percent decrease between the 1994-1995 mean and 2012 (Table S3-2).

The 1994-2012 average of manure P as a percentage of manure plus fertilizer P was highest for the two St. Marys sites and the closest downstream site MAUN (42 to 52%, in Table S3-2); annual percent values for 2012 were slightly higher than the 1994-2012 averages. Manure N proportions of the sum of manure plus fertilizer N were consistently lower than manure P proportions for the WLEB sites, and, similar to the manure P results, were highest for the St. Marys sites and the site MAUN (28 to 37%, in Table S3-3).

Manure and livestock estimates by watershed area can be influenced by a number of factors including screening of CAFOs, for which permitting, reporting, and classification systems can vary by state, as well as assumptions regarding transport distances of manure from livestock operations (Long et al., 2018; International Joint Commission, 2018). Variations in manure-estimation methods, such as weighting or not weighting county-based estimates according to locations of agricultural land use within watersheds, also can result in differences between estimates (LimnoTech, 2017, p.37). In the vicinity of the St. Marys watershed, some larger CAFOs in the southern half of Mercer County occur within a region that extends to 20- to 25-km south of the watershed boundary (LimnoTech, 2017); however, numerous CAFOs are also located within the watershed (Long et al., 2017; Colleen Long, Univ. Michigan, written commun., July 21, 2017; Indiana Department of Agriculture, 2017).

Manure nutrients typically are distributed in fairly close proximity to the source of manure production (Ohio Lake Erie Phosphorus Task Force, 2013); however, distances of such transport likely vary by manure type and over time, and documentation on manure distribution is not readily available (Long et al., 2018; International Joint Commission, 2018).

Regional-scale 2003-2012 estimates of fertilizer application practices for the WLEB based on farm surveys comparing 2003-2006 and 2012 are described in U.S. Department of Agriculture (2017). These estimates indicate an increase in soil incorporation (increase from 29 to 43% of cropland acres for N and from 45 to 60% for P), and appropriate timing of fertilizer applications (near time of planting) in about 54-60 percent of croplands for N and 63-71 percent for P. Fertilizer application rates were similar during both periods and exceeded crop use of N by more than 40 percent in less than 5 percent of croplands. The practice of applying less P than plant removal rates was widespread (52 and 58% of croplands during the 2003-2006 and 2012 periods) but exceeded 60 percent of crop needs in 13 percent of croplands during these periods.

Changes in usage patterns of different chemical formulations of P fertilizers applied on croplands between the 1990s to 2011 have been documented in Ohio and are likely indicative of usage patterns in the WLEB; however, given the generally high solubility of all these formulations, possible influences of such differences on P loss are uncertain (Ohio Lake Erie Phosphorus Task Force, 2013). These formulations include diammonium phosphate, triple superphosphate, monoammonium phosphate, and ammonium polyphosphate. Changes in the chemical formulations of P fertilizers applied on croplands between the 1990s to 2011 in Ohio (Ohio Lake Erie Phosphorus Task Force, 2013) show that during the 1990s to 2007, diammonium phosphate (DAP) had the largest usage with a peak in applications during 1993-1996 nearly twice that of prior or subsequent periods, with a decreasing trend in triple superphosphate (TSP), which has been little used since about 2006. During recent years (2006-2011), DAP, monoammonium phosphate, and ammonium polyphosphate show similar usage amounts. A shift over the past 1 to 2 decades to greater use of monoammonium phosphate and less use of diammonium phosphate in the WLEB has also been noted, although limited records are available (International Joint Commission, 2018).

Crop Production

From 2003 to 2012, crop rotations in the WLEB were dominated by corn-soybean (51-56% of cropland), followed by corn-soybean-wheat (21-23%), and soybean-wheat (7-13%) (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2016). Proportions of crop types in the 9 WLEB watersheds include soybeans (44-55% of row crop area), corn (25-44%), and winter wheat (9-20%) (2009 data in Falcone, 2017a and b). Crop-production data are reported at 5-year intervals for the study sites in Falcone (2017a and b). The most noteworthy differences in crop production between 1992 and 2012 at the WLEB study sites were the increases in soybean production (by 30 to 45% at most of the sites) occurring predominantly between 2002 and 2012, and the 3 sites in the Sandusky basin exhibit a decrease in wheat and an increase in corn production (Figs. S3-5 and S3-6). The pattern in the Raisin basin differed somewhat from the other sites, showing a decrease in corn, increase in wheat, and little change in soybean production. Changes in crop production over time in the WLEB may reflect both changes in acreage as well as increased crop yields over time (e.g. Richards et al., 2002 and 2009).

Figure S3-1. Change in percent of cropland in conservation tillage or high-residue management for watersheds in the Maumee, Raisin, and Sandusky River basins (from Jarvie et al, 2017; and Remegio Confesor, written commun., April 2017). [SAND, Sandusky River watershed; RAIS, River Raisin watershed; MAUM, Maumee River watershed; HUC, Hydrologic Unit Code: StJoeHUC8, code 04100003 St. Joseph River watershed; StMarysHUC8, code 04100004 St. Marys River watershed]

Figure S3-2. Time series of watershed mean livestock estimates for study sites in the western Lake Erie drainage basin (from Falcone, 2017a and b). Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper).

Figure S3-3. Time series of watershed mean estimates of fertilizer-P and -N (1987-2012) and manure-P and -N (1982-2012), by site. (Falcone, 2017b). Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper).

Figure S3-4. Watershed mean annual fertilizer and manure (A) phosphorus and (B) nitrogen during the 1992-2012 period upstream from each study site. (Data from Falcone, 2017a and b). Sites are ranked by 1992-2012 median values of fertilizer. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper). [Fert, fertilizer; N, nitrogen content; P, phosphorus content]

Figure S3-5. Changes in corn, wheat, and soybean production between 1992 and 2012, by watershed, for sites in the western Lake Erie drainage basin (Falcone, 2017b). Values are derived using watershed means, in bushels per square kilometer. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper).

Figure S3-6. Time series of 1982-2012 watershed mean estimates of (a) corn, (b) wheat, and (c) soybean production for sites in the western Lake Erie drainage basin (Falcone, 2017a and b). Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper).

Table S3-1. Summary of reservoir storage and streamflow alterations upstream of the study sites.

Site abbreviation	USGS stream-gage number	Streamgage name	Number of dams upstream, 2009 ¹	Pre-1990 total reservoir storage ¹ in watershed (in number of days of mean annual streamflow ²)	Total reservoir storage ¹ in watershed, 2009 (in number of days of mean annual streamflow ²)	Normal reservoir storage ¹ in watershed, 2009 (in number of days of mean annual streamflow ²)	Additional remarks on flow alterations ³
RAIS	04176500	River Raisin near Monroe, MI	22	59	59	43	Diurnal fluctuation caused by power plants upstream from station prior to June 27, 1968. At times, flow is affected by irrigation pumpage.
STMD	04181500	St. Marys River at Decatur, IN	3	0.7	0.7	0	Flow regulated by Grand Lake. Slight diversion from or into Wabash River Basin and into Miami and Erie Canal.
STMF	04182000	St. Marys River near Ft. Wayne, IN	3	0.5	0.5	0	The flow is sometimes regulated by Grand Lake. Slight diversion from or into Wabash River Basin and into Miami and Erie Canal. During extreme floods, some water bypasses gage and flows through Houk Ditch and Paul Trier Ditch into the Maumee River.
STJO	04180500	St. Joseph River near Ft. Wayne, IN	32	26	26	14	Flow regulated by Cedarville Reservoir and some flow diverted into storage of Hurshtown Reservoir.
MAUN	04183000	Maumee River at New Haven, IN	40	28	28	23	Flow regulated by hydropower plants on the St. Joseph River 10.3 mi upstream from station. Flow slightly regulated by upstream reservoirs.
MAUW	04193500	Maumee River near Waterville, OH	94	20	20	16	
ROCK	04197170	Rock Creek at Tiffin, OH	0	0	0	0	USGS Hydroclimatic Data Network (HCDN) gage (Lins, 2012), and GAGES-II reference-quality streamflow classification (Falcone, 2015).
HONE	04197100	Honey Creek at Melmore, OH	6	0.5	1.6	0.7	USGS Hydroclimatic Data Network (HCDN) gage (Lins, 2012), and GAGES-II reference-quality streamflow classification (Falcone, 2015).
SAND	04198000	Sandusky River near Fremont, OH	28	7.6	8.6	6.3	
CUYA	04181500	Cuyahoga River at Independence, OH	56	52	52	22	Natural flow of stream affected by diversion, storage reservoirs, and power plants. Some diversion from the Tuscarawas River Basin drainage into this basin at Portage Lakes (see REMARKS for station 03117000). Water diverted into Ohio Canal at Brecksville, 6 mi upstream from station, bypasses station.
¹ Source: GAGES-II database: Falcone et al. (2010); Falcone (2011 and 2015).							
² Mean annual streamflow (cubic meters per second per day) for the period 1980-2015; streamflow values for ROCK and STJO are means for the 1984-2015 period of available record. (U.S. Geological Survey, 2017)							
³ U.S. Geological Survey National Water Information System web site, accessed March 2017 (U.S. Geological Survey, 2017)							

Table S3-2. Comparison of watershed mean estimates of manure phosphorus and farm fertilizer phosphorus between 1994 and 2012. Years were selected for comparison to 1995-2015 trends; manure data were reported at 5-year intervals; fertilizer data were reported annually. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper). (Data from Falcone, 2017a and b).

Site abbreviation	Streamgage number	1994-2012 Manure-P (watershed mean values)					1994-2012 Fertilizer-P (watershed mean values)					Manure plus fertilizer P: watershed mean	Manure-P as percent of (farm fertilizer-P plus manure-P)	
		1994 ¹ (kg-P/km ² per yr)	2012 (kg-P/km ² per yr)	1994-2012 mean annual (kg-P/km ² per year)	Change between 1994 and 2012 (kg-P/km ²)	Change between 1994 and 2012, as percent of 1994 value	1994-1995 mean (kg-P/km ² per year)	2012 (kg-P/km ² per year)	1994-2012 mean annual (kg-P/km ² per year)	Change between 1994-1995 and 2012 (kg-P/km ²)	Change between 1994-1995 and 2012, as percent of 1994-1995 mean	1994-2012 mean annual (kg-P/km ² per year)	1994-2012 Mean (kg-P/km ² per year)	2012 (percent)
RAIS	04176500	198	163	166	-35	-17.6	814	433	622	-380	-46.8	788	21	27
STJO	04180500	243	238	230	-6	-2.4	742	716	719	-27	-3.6	950	24	25
STMD	04181500	1,158	1,675	1,487	516	44.6	1,603	1,088	1,359	-515	-32.1	2,846	52	61
STMF	04182000	1,081	1,517	1,362	436	40.3	1,506	1,116	1,305	-391	-25.9	2,667	51	58
MAUN	04183000	565	733	668	168	29.7	1,014	844	919	-170	-16.8	1,586	42	46
MAUW	04193500	353	435	381	82	23.2	1,301	903	1,090	-398	-30.6	1,471	26	33
HONE	04197100	258	293	258	35	13.7	1,657	1,214	1,358	-443	-26.7	1,616	16	19
ROCK	04197170	228	216	198	-12	-5.2	1,457	1,045	1,180	-412	-28.3	1,378	14	17
SAND	04198000	241	301	255	60	25.1	1,603	1,079	1,278	-524	-32.7	1,533	17	22
CUYA	04208000	75	75	69	1	0.9	155	83	129	-72	-46.3	198	35	48
Summary for the nine watersheds in the western Lake Erie drainage basin:														
Mean		481	619	556	138	17	1,300	938	1,092	-362	-27	1,648	29	34
Maximum		1,158	1,675	1,487	516	45	1,657	1,214	1,359	-27	-4	2,846	52	61
Minimum		198	163	166	-35	-18	742	433	622	-524	-47	788	14	17

¹ Interpolated, using 1992 and 1997 reported values.

Table S3-3. Comparison of watershed mean estimates of manure nitrogen and farm fertilizer nitrogen between 1994 and 2012. Years were selected for comparison to 1995-2015 trends; manure data were reported at 5-year intervals; fertilizer data were reported annually. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper). (Data from Falcone, 2017a and b)

Site abbreviation	Streamgage number	1994-2012 Manure-N (watershed mean values)					1994-2012 Fertilizer-N (watershed mean values)					Manure plus fertilizer N: watershed mean	Manure-N as percent of (farm fertilizer-N plus manure-N)	
		1994 ¹ (kg-N/km ² per yr)	2012 (kg-N/km ² per yr)	1994-2012 mean annual (kg-N/km ² per year)	Change between 1994 and 2012 (kg-P/km ²)	Change between 1994 and 2012, as percent of 1994 value	1994-1995 mean (kg-N/km ² per year)	2012 (kg-N/km ² per year)	1994-2012 mean annual (kg-N/km ² per year)	Change between 1994-1995 and 2012 (kg-N/km ²)	Change between 1994-1995 and 2012, as percent of 1994-1995 mean	1994-2012 mean annual (kg-N/km ² per year)	1994-2012 Mean (kg-N/km ² per year)	2012 (percent)
RAIS	04176500	746	727	703	-19	-2.6	4,467	3,440	3,944	-1,027	-23.0	4,647	15	17
STJO	04180500	853	877	852	24	2.8	4,193	4,661	4,266	468	11.2	5,118	17	16
STMD	04181500	3,519	4,881	4,330	1,362	38.7	9,148	6,297	7,516	-2,850	-31.2	11,846	37	44
STMF	04182000	3,278	4,459	3,976	1,182	36.1	8,593	6,666	7,328	-1,928	-22.4	11,304	35	40
MAUN	04183000	1,778	2,251	2,049	473	26.6	5,761	5,259	5,285	-503	-8.7	7,334	28	30
MAUW	04193500	1,085	1,372	1,193	288	26.5	7,421	5,175	6,010	-2,246	-30.3	7,203	17	21
HONE	04197100	781	829	760	48	6.2	9,473	6,513	7,310	-2,960	-31.2	8,070	9	11
ROCK	04197170	676	600	592	-76	-11.2	8,328	5,606	6,351	-2,722	-32.7	6,943	9	10
SAND	04198000	721	820	732	99	13.8	9,164	5,789	6,867	-3,375	-36.8	7,599	10	12
CUYA	04208000	346	347	321	1	0.3	880	446	694	-434	-49.3	1,014	32	44
Summary for the nine watersheds in the western Lake Erie drainage basin:														
Mean		1,493	1,869	1,688	376	15	7,394	5,490	6,098	-1,905	-23	7,785	20	22
Maximum		3,519	4,881	4,330	1,362	39	9,473	6,666	7,516	468	11	11,846	37	44
Minimum		676	600	592	-76	-11	4,193	3,440	3,944	-3,375	-37	4,647	9	10

¹ Interpolated, using 1992 and 1997 reported values.

Table S3-4. Fertilizer application rates by crop type during 1995-2015 in Indiana, Michigan, and Ohio.
Data are statewide averages from U.S. Department of Agriculture (2018).

State	1995-2015 Average N-fertilizer applied (kg/ha yr ⁻¹)			1995-2015 Average P-fertilizer applied (kg/ha yr ⁻¹)		
	Corn	Soybeans	Wheat	Corn	Soybeans	Wheat
Indiana	167	28	97	77	61	71
Michigan	136	18	107	51	47	53
Ohio	177	21	100	81	57	70
Average (IN, MI, OH):	160	23	101	70	55	64
Ohio	177	21	100	81	57	70
Percent of crop acres receiving fertilizer (OH: 1995-2015 average)	100%	21%	97%	91%	28%	86%

Appendix S4: Quantile-Kendall Results for Flow Trends by Month

Quantile-Kendall analysis (Hirsch, 2018) and construction of Quantile-Kendall plots are described in the paper under the section “Exploring Streamflow Trends”, and a more detailed description of the methodology is provided in Appendix S1. Refer to Table 1 in the paper for definitions of the site abbreviations.

Figure S4-1 (available at ESM link: “ESM Figure S4-1: Monthly Quantile-Kendall Plots By Site”) shows Quantile-Kendall plots by month for each site (120 plots) based on daily mean discharge (streamflow) records for the period April 1, 1994, through March 31, 2016 (referenced to climatic years). There were variations in flow trend patterns among these sites for some months, however, increasing trends encompassing high flows are consistent among the majority of these sites for the months March and November through December. High-flow increases during December are apparent at all sites (upper 2 quartiles flow range), including CUYA, with trend slopes showing an increase of as much as 6 to 10 percent per year. Increases in flows during spring months are most apparent during March (less so during April), which shows spatially consistent increases in the upper 2 quartiles of flows across all sites (1-4% per year) with low-flow increases at some of the sites. Stow et al. (2015) also show increases in average flows for March and December in the Maumee River during approximately the same time frame (1990-2013). High-flow trends during summer months varied across these study sites and show both negative and positive changes.

Monthly trends in the range of low-to-medium-flow trends (lower 2 quartiles) show less consistency among sites compared to high-flow trends. January low-to-medium flows show increases in the range of 2 to 8% per year at all 10 sites except RAIS, and little or negative changes in higher flows. The majority of sites (7 of 10) show moderate increases (<4% per year) in low to medium flows during June. Low- to medium-flow increasing trends with strong likelihood (exceeding 90%) occurred during April in the upper Maumee River basin at the two St. Marys sites and the MAUW site (ranging from about 2 to 6% per year), and during October at the ROCK and HONE sites (ranging from about 3 to 10% per year).

Figure S4-1: Monthly Quantile-Kendall Plots of flow trends for the 10 study sites (see separate ESM link: “ESM Figure S4-1: Monthly Quantile-Kendall Plots By Site”).

Appendix S5: Recent decadal nutrient trends: 2005-2015

Recent decadal trends were analyzed using Weighted Regressions on Time, Discharge, and Season (WRTDS) and the method of flow normalization under the stationary streamflow assumption (FNS), which is appropriate for this relatively short time period. The FNS trend methodology is equivalent to the WRTDS “flow normalized” trend methodology as described originally in Hirsch et al. (2010) and Hirsch and De Cicco (2015), and the FNS trends are equivalent to the CQTCs (concentration-discharge trend components) described in the WRTDS generalized flow normalization (FNG) methodology (see “Evaluating nutrient trends” in the paper).

The uncertainty about the FNS trend estimates, including confidence intervals and the likelihood that the sign of the trend is correct, is determined using a block bootstrap procedure described by Hirsch et al. (2015). During the 2005-2015 period, all of the WLEB sites show increases in SRP although most of these increases were minimal, particularly in contrast to the 1995-2015 SRP trends (Fig. S1 and Table S1); and the majority of sites show decreasing trends in TP and TN (Fig. S5-1 and Table S5-1). The SRP increases for 4 of the 5 WLEB SRP sites, though considered likely, are minimal (+3 to +8%); Honey Creek (HONE) shows a somewhat larger, highly likely increasing trend (31%). In contrast, at the Cuyahoga River site there was a highly likely decrease in SRP and TP (-46 and -30%, respectively), and decreases in TN, which likely reflects much lower area in row crops and increased influence of point sources and may be related to both wastewater treatment plant improvements and reductions in nonpoint source loads during this period in this basin as discussed by Baker et al. (2014).

Out of the 9 WLEB TP sites, only the Honey Creek (HONE) and the upper St. Marys (STMD) sites show likely increasing TP trends (+15%). The TP reductions at the majority of WLEB sites likely reflect the widespread agricultural management efforts including the increase in conservation tillage (Fig. S3-1) in these watersheds that have focused on erosion control. Factors driving the phosphorus (TP and SRP) increases at HONE and STMD may include livestock and manure-P increases (St. Marys basin), higher amounts of fertilizer-P usage watershed-mean) at these sites relative to the other sites, and (or) in the Honey Creek basin the changes in proportions of croplands planted in corn and wheat during this period inferred from the crop production estimates (Figs. S3-2 through S3-6; Tables S3-2 and S3-3).

Although the majority of WLEB sites show very likely decreasing TP and TN trends, in contrast the upper St. Marys basin site (STMD) shows increases in TP and TN (by +15 to +16%). Highly likely decreases in TN (-22 to -24%) occurred in River Raisin, Sandusky River, and Rock Creek; and all sites in the Sandusky River basin show negative TN trends (Fig. S5-1c). The TP and TN increases at site STMD contrast with minimal negative TP and TN trends downstream at the St. Marys site (STMF), which suggests, given that percent row-crop area (Table 1 in paper) and fertilizer usage are similar for both sites (Fig. S3-3; Tables S3-1 and S3-2), other factors may contribute to these observed differences. Additional research is needed to confirm causes for this difference in trends between the STMD and STMF sites; it could relate to the growth of livestock operations and manure occurring in the upper parts of the basin (Fig. S3-4; Tables S1 and S2) and possibly the nearby availability of manure sources for use as fertilizer given the proximity of the numerous livestock operations (CAFOs) outside but near the upper St. Marys River basin (Colleen Long, Univ. Michigan, written commun., July 21, 2017; LimnoTech, 2017). It is notable that the three sites in the WLEB for which negative trends in TP were highly likely (RAIS, MAUW, and ROCK) also show, in contrast, small positive SRP trends— although the probabilities associated with the SRP trend directions were lower than those for TP (Fig. S5-1).

Figure S5-1. Recent decadal trends (2005-2015) in annual yields of soluble reactive phosphorus, total phosphorus, and total nitrogen at each of the study sites. The trends were determined using the method of Weighted Regressions on Time, Discharge, and Season (WRTDS) and stationary flow normalization (FNS). Asterisk symbols indicate the likelihood that the estimated trend direction is correct. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper). [SRP, soluble reactive phosphorus, as P; TP, total phosphorus, as P; TN, total nitrogen, as N].

Table S5-1. Summary of 2005-2015 trends in annual nutrient fluxes at the study sites. Flux values (as yield) were determined using the method of stationary flow normalization. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper). [FNS, stationary flow normalized trend; CI, confidence interval; SRP, soluble reactive phosphorus, as P; TP, total phosphorus, as P; TN, total nitrogen, as N; Likelihood level descriptors: * (likely), 67 to <90%; ** (very likely), 90 to <95%; *** (highly likely), 95 to 100%; U (uncertain), 33 to <67%]]

Site abbreviation	Parameter	FNS trend (kg/km ²)	FNS trend (% of 2005 yield)	Lower 90% CI of FNS trend (kg/km ²)	Upper 90% CI of FNS trend (kg/km ²)	Likelihood of FNS-trend direction	Likelihood level	FNS annual yield, 2005 (kg/km ²)	FNS annual yield, 2015 (kg/km ²)
CUYA	SRP	-10.8	-46	-13.2	-9.0	0.988	***	23.3	12.5
ROCK	SRP	1.5	5.4	-5.1	9.9	0.671	*	28.8	30.3
HONE	SRP	11.3	31	4.4	16.1	0.971	***	37.3	48.9
SAND	SRP	2.6	7.8	-1.9	5.7	0.793	*	32.8	35.4
MAUW	SRP	2.3	7.4	-2.4	5.8	0.892	*	31.4	33.7
RAIS	SRP	0.4	2.7	-2.6	5.6	0.695	*	13.3	13.7
CUYA	TP	-44.9	-30	-64.4	-27.6	0.988	***	151	106
ROCK	TP	-15.4	-9.7	-44.0	0.1	0.951	***	159	143
HONE	TP	18.9	15	-7.5	37.3	0.866	*	131	150
SAND	TP	-13.1	-8.9	-43.4	5.3	0.892	*	148	135
STMD	TP	22.2	15	-11.9	66.7	0.89	*	153	175
STMF	TP	-4.1	-2.3	-41.5	19.7	0.646	U	174	170
STJO	TP	-11.6	-15	-27.9	7.0	0.89	*	75.4	63.8
MAUN	TP	-6.1	-5.1	-41.1	4.7	0.817	*	120	114
MAUW	TP	-13.5	-10	-34.7	-2.0	0.989	***	129	115
RAIS	TP	-13.8	-26	-20.5	-5.4	0.988	***	53.0	39.3
CUYA	TN	-83.1	-5.7	-136	33.1	0.89	*	1,447	1,365
ROCK	TN	-406	-24	-683	-87.8	0.971	***	1,700	1,300
HONE	TN	-292	-13	-723	93.3	0.866	*	2,176	1,886
SAND	TN	-520	-22	-1,004	-29.7	0.971	***	2,389	1,867
STMD	TN	426	16	-191	1,114	0.9	**	2,730	3,153
STMF	TN	-220	-7.8	-591	292	0.866	*	2,817	2,599
STJO	TN	132	11	-329	633	0.72	*	1,257	1,392
MAUN	TN	138	6.9	-322	528	0.573	U	1,991	2,128
MAUW	TN	-272	-12	-746	245	0.866	*	2,263	1,988
RAIS	TN	-368	-24	-758	-76.4	0.971	***	1,538	1,171

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Additional ESM Figures and Tables

Figure S1. Multidecadal trends (1995-2015) in annual yields of phosphorus and nitrogen parameters at each of the study sites, showing change in yield (kg/km²) and change as percent of 1995 yield. The trends were determined using Weighted Regressions on Time, Discharge, and Season (WRTDS) and the method of generalized flow normalization for nonstationary streamflow effects. Red arrows indicate increasing trend and green arrows indicate decreasing trend; arrow width is proportional to trend magnitude. See Table 1 (in paper) for additional site details.

[SRP, soluble reactive phosphorus, as P; TP, total phosphorus, as P; NO₂₃, nitrate plus nitrite, as N; TN, total nitrogen, as N; and TKN, total Kjeldahl nitrogen, as N. At site STMD, the TN and TKN trends correspond to the period 1999-2015 and change is percent of 1999 yield.]

Figure S2. Comparison of 1995 and 2015 molar nutrient ratios of (A) TN:TP and (B) NO23:SRP at each site, calculated from yields based on generalized flow normalization. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper). [na, data not available; for site STMD, 1999 and 2015 TN fluxes were compared, based on limited data available.]

Figure S3. Comparison of 1995 and 2015 total phosphorus yields for all sites, determined using generalized flow normalization. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper).

Table S1. Summary of 1995-2015 trends in annual fluxes of five nutrient parameters at the study sites. Flux values (as yield) were derived using the method of generalized flow normalization. Site abbreviations are defined in Table 1 (in the paper).

[FNG, Generalized flow normalization; CQTC, concentration-discharge trend component; QTC, discharge trend component; CI, confidence interval; SRP, soluble reactive phosphorus, as P; TP, total phosphorus, as P; NO23, nitrate plus nitrite, as N; TN, total nitrogen, as N; TKN, total Kjeldahl nitrogen, as N; Likelihood descriptors and p-levels: * (likely), 67 to 90%; ** (very likely), 90 to 95%; *** (highly likely), 95 to 100%; U (uncertain), 33 to <67%]

Site abbreviation	Parameter	FNG trend (kg/km ²)	FNG trend (% of 1995 yield)	FNG trend direction	Likelihood of FNG trend direction	Likelihood level	CQTC (kg/km ²)	QTC (kg/km ²)	CQTC (% of 1995 yield)	QTC (% of 1995 yield)	Lower 90% CI (kg/km ²)	Upper 90% CI (kg/km ²)	FNG annual yield, 1995 (kg/km ² per year)	FNG annual yield, 2015 (kg/km ² per year)
RAIS	SRP	8.2	109	up	0.999	***	5.9	2.3	78.7	30.1	5.0	13.4	7.5	15.7
MAUW	SRP	20.0	109	up	0.999	***	14.1	5.9	77.3	32.1	15.9	24.2	18.2	38.2
SAND	SRP	29.9	230	up	0.999	***	19.1	10.8	147	82.9	26.6	32.4	13.0	42.9
HONE	SRP	45.7	322	up	0.999	***	32.1	13.6	227	95.7	38.8	51.9	14.2	59.9
ROCK	SRP	23.5	208	up	0.999	***	17.4	6.0	154	53.6	16.6	29.3	11.3	34.7
CUYA	SRP	-0.3	-2.3		0.592	U	-2.0	1.7	-14.5	12.2	-2.8	2.0	13.5	13.2
RAIS	TP	-7.0	-14.0	down	0.841	*	-14.6	7.6	-29.2	15.2	-13.9	3.9	50.0	43.0
MAUW	TP	6.3	5.1		0.648	U	-30.0	36.3	-24.0	29.1	-17.3	20.8	125	131
MAUN	TP	4.3	3.8		0.488	U	-13.5	17.8	-11.9	15.8	-27.8	21.4	113	117
STJO	TP	-36.0	-36.0	down	0.997	***	-35.1	-0.9	-35.1	-0.9	-60.7	-20.8	100	64
STMD	TP	82.1	71.1	up	0.995	***	30.2	51.9	26.1	45.0	41.6	128	115	198
STMF	TP	75.7	67.1	up	0.999	***	26.7	49.0	23.7	43.4	48.3	97.2	113	188
SAND	TP	40.6	33.7	up	0.987	***	-24.0	64.6	-19.9	53.6	11.7	60.5	121	161
HONE	TP	67.7	58.2	up	0.999	***	-2.6	70.3	-2.2	60.4	41.9	87.8	116	184
ROCK	TP	18.7	12.7	up	0.797	*	-34.5	53.2	-23.5	36.3	-20.0	44.1	147	165
CUYA	TP	-4.3	-3.5		0.652	U	-46.1	41.8	-36.9	33.4	-30.4	18.3	125	121
RAIS	NO23	-174	-15.3	down	0.825	*	-266	92.7	-23.4	8.2	-416	138	1,136	963
MAUW	NO23	-129	-7.2	down	0.704	*	-414	285	-23.3	16.0	-501	205	1,778	1,649
MAUN	NO23	261	19.6	up	0.921	**	163	98.5	12.2	7.4	-64.4	718	1,330	1,591
STJO	NO23	80.2	8.3		0.664	U	109	-28.7	11.3	-3.0	-277	429	966	1,046
STMD	NO23	577	28.8	up	0.893	*	-5.8	583	-0.3	29.1	-188	1,289	2,005	2,582
STMF	NO23	395	23.4	up	0.891	*	-111	506	-6.6	30.0	-165	857	1,690	2,085
SAND	NO23	-132	-7.7	down	0.730	*	-633	501	-37.0	29.2	-505	203	1,713	1,580
HONE	NO23	44.9	2.9		0.534	U	-426	471	-27.6	30.5	-390	511	1,544	1,589
ROCK	NO23	-133	-13.1	down	0.803	*	-358	225	-35.1	22.0	-448	120	1,020	887
CUYA	NO23	41.1	5.1	up	0.877	*	-39.0	80.1	-4.8	10.0	-18.5	94.5	805	846
RAIS	TN	-180	-12.8	down	0.807	*	-264	83.5	-18.8	5.9	-424	164	1,407	1,227
MAUW	TN	-52.0	-2.3		0.628	U	-469	417	-20.7	18.4	-486	320	2,261	2,209
MAUN	TN	260	13.7	up	0.863	*	102	159	5.4	8.4	-140	732	1,894	2,155
STJO	TN	-38.3	-2.6		0.566	U	-17.6	-20.7	-1.2	-1.4	-405	305	1,456	1,418
STMD	TN	466	15.6	up	0.835	*	-282	748	-9.5	25.1	-331	1,440	2,977	3,443
STMF	TN	606	27.5	up	0.953	***	-68.7	675	-3.1	30.7	21.5	1,095	2,201	2,807
SAND	TN	-44.8	-2.0		0.542	U	-773	728	-35.0	33.0	-489	365	2,208	2,163
HONE	TN	184	9.1	up	0.746	*	-519	703	-25.5	34.6	-283	637	2,032	2,216
ROCK	TN	-119	-7.5	down	0.748	*	-520	402	-32.9	25.4	-533	176	1,583	1,464
CUYA	TN	173	13.6	up	0.989	***	-49.9	223	-3.9	17.5	46.4	296	1,274	1,448
RAIS	TKN	20.0	7.1	up	0.817	*	-0.6	20.5	-0.2	7.3	-30.0	62.8	281	301
MAUW	TKN	87.8	17.1	up	0.889	*	-39.4	127	-7.7	24.8	-23.5	162	512	600
MAUN	TKN	-12.0	-2.1	down	0.714	*	-72.5	60.5	-12.7	10.6	-123	51.1	568	556
STJO	TKN	-86.3	-17.8	down	0.833	*	-77.4	-8.9	-16.0	-1.8	-125	-34.8	485	398
STMD	TKN	291	55.7	up	0.997	***	98.9	192	18.9	36.8	160	470	522	814
STMF	TKN	214	38.3	up	0.999	***	7.4	207	1.3	37.0	94.8	292	558	773
SAND	TKN	85.5	16.7	up	0.963	***	-142	227	-27.7	44.5	6.9	146	511	596
HONE	TKN	136	28.1	up	0.989	***	-93.0	229	-19.2	47.3	41.3	208	484	619
ROCK	TKN	14.4	2.5		0.502	U	-169	184	-29.6	32.1	-138	91.1	572	586
CUYA	TKN	125	27.4	up	0.987	***	-18.2	143	-4.0	31.3	36.8	194	457	582

Table S2. Comparisons of 1995 and 2015 nutrient flux ratios for the study sites. Ratios (molar) are based on nutrient fluxes determined using the method of generalized flow normalization. Details on site locations and site abbreviations are in the paper (Fig. 1 and Table 1).

[SRP, soluble reactive phosphorus, as P; TP, total phosphorus, as P; NO_x, nitrate plus nitrite, as N; TN, total nitrogen, as N; na, SRP data not available]

Site abbreviation	SRP:TP yield		PP:TP yield		NO _x :SRP yield		NO _x :TN yield		TN:TP yield	
	1995	2015	1995	2015	1995	2015	1995	2015	1995	2015
RAIS	0.15	0.37	0.85	0.63	333	135	0.81	0.78	62	63
MAUW	0.15	0.29	0.85	0.71	215	95	0.79	0.75	40	37
SAND	0.11	0.27	0.89	0.73	292	82	0.78	0.73	40	30
HONE	0.12	0.33	0.88	0.67	241	59	0.76	0.72	39	27
ROCK	0.08	0.21	0.92	0.79	200	56	0.64	0.61	24	20
MAUN	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.70	0.74	37	41
STJO	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.66	0.74	32	49
STMD ¹	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.67	0.75	57	39
STMF	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.77	0.74	43	33
CUYA	0.11	0.11	0.89	0.89	132	142	0.63	0.58	23	27
Average of WLEB sites ² :	0.12	0.29	0.88	0.71	256	85	0.73	0.73	42	37

¹ TN values for STMD correspond to 1999, based on limited monitoring record at this site.

² WLEB (western Lake Erie drainage basin) sites include all sites except CUYA.